

New and conventional media to senior high school student's reading motivation

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ABSTRACT

Motivation has long been established as an important factor that affects reading among students. With the advent of technology, reading motivation has become more nuanced as new reading media alongside conventional media surfaced. The study explored the relationship between senior high school students' new and conventional media preferences and their reading motivation. A descriptive correlational research design was employed to analyze the data and determine correlations between variables. Results revealed that students generally have a stronger preference for books (physical books, school books, and pocketbooks) as reading media. Students also have a stronger preference for reading academic texts in print formats. In terms of the amount of time spent on reading electronic and print texts, students generally spend longer time reading electronic texts. The results also showed higher intrinsic motivation to read than extrinsic motivation among students. Finally, significant positive relationships were found between most intrinsic motivation scales and students' new media preferences. Few significant positive relationships were found between extrinsic motivation scales and students' new media preferences. Implications of these findings highlighted the need to utilize both conventional and new media and consider students' preferences vis-à-vis classroom reading tasks.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology and the adoption of contemporary pedagogies have created an opportunity for educational institutions to shift from using conventional media to using new media as learning tools. This educational shift also answers the call to strengthen the digitizing processes in the education sector [1]. Using new media like technology as the most up-to-date instructional medium creates opportunities for students to be exposed to new authentic and meaningful learning experiences encouraging a more enjoyable and productive learning environment [2]. In addition, it provides the opportunity for the students to work collaboratively and easily access the information that can supplement their learning experience. Since then, the use of new media has permeated all aspects of education.

Countless studies have established that technology and new media are beneficial supplements to the education system. Studies show that many students prefer using new media due to its perceived effect on their academic performance, especially on their reading. Corcoran [3] indicated that the use of new media (tablet apps) affects the reading instruction of first-grade students. Students using tablet apps are found to perform

better than the ones not using them. Similarly, the 2016 Digital Study Trends Survey report showed that four out of five (81%) college students claim that digital learning technology helps improve their grades, and more than two-thirds (69%) said that it helps them to focus [4]. Likewise, half of the students who have utilized adaptive learning technologies and online quizzes indicate that these tools have a “significant effect” on their grades, making them the most effective tools. Likewise, new media is found to be beneficial to college reading, as evidenced by a study of 500 tertiary-level students [5]. The existence of modern media has significantly impacted their reading habits. The study’s conclusions demonstrate how using new media to learn the English language greatly inspires students, turns them from dependent and passive to independent and eager learners, and serves as a complement to classroom instruction. This demonstrates unequivocally how crucial new media is to support high reading proficiency.

Similarly, educational institutions in the Philippines are not new to using media (conventional and new) in the classroom. The high expectations from teachers to be able to integrate technology prompted more effective teaching-learning and training initiatives [6], [7]. Further, the curriculum has been integrating technology in the classroom through the use of learning management systems (LMS) and open educational resources (OER). The impact of technology on education has long been recognized but has been reinforced by the school closures in the country because of the pandemic. The sudden shift from in-person learning to online and distance learning has pushed educators and institutions to rely on technology (mainly new media) to aid instruction. Although the use of technology as a potent educational tool has gained widespread acceptance, there do seem to be some concerns regarding its usage in language and reading. Even though many educational institutions have new media available, it remains common to meet students who dislike reading. It is still a challenge for Filipino educators and institutions to drive students to become fully engaged readers. Many children and adolescents lack motivation and engagement in reading [8]; 40% of pupils from 50 nations reported being only “somewhat” or “less than” involved in their reading sessions on average [9]. The abrupt transition from face-to-face classroom instruction to online/blended/modular learning left students on their own to complete assignments utilizing the resources at their disposal.

Modern media has made it easier to obtain reading materials. Open-source libraries are becoming more popular, and reading has become more convenient. Though it is usual to link reading motivation to academic accomplishment, this study also tries to determine how modern media may have changed students’ reading, or whether it has made reading a “pleasant” experience for them. Studies have claimed that students are affected by new media and prefer using them; thus, finding a relationship between new media usage and reading motivation may be confirmed in this study. This study investigates the relationship between students’ new media preferences and their reading motivation. Specifically, this answers the following questions:

- i) What are the SHS students’ media reading profiles in terms of new and conventional media reading preferences; text type preference; and, reading amount?
- ii) What are the students’ dominant reading motivation types?
- iii) Is there a significant correlation between students’ new media preferences and reading motivation?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study employed descriptive-correlational research design to collect quantifiable and inferential statistics on senior high school (SHS) students’ new media preferences, text types read (print and electronic), reading amount, and reading motivation type. This is an approach of descriptive research that blends quantitative and qualitative data to provide relevant and accurate information. Descriptive research is the intentional process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about current conditions, practices, trends, and cause-and-effect relationships to then interpret the data appropriately and accurately [10]. Pearson correlation was also used to understand significant relationships between variables. Due to the number of media (traditional and new) utilized by students in the region, this study focused on but is not limited to, the following types of media: blogs, mail, social media networks, websites, E-books, newspapers, books, and magazines.

2.2. Research participants

The respondents to the study were 201 senior high school students enrolled in the academic year 2022-2023. These students belong to the upper secondary education level following the Philippine K-12 Basic Education Curriculum. These students are within, but not limited to, the ages of 17 and 19. Participants are from varied learning institutions in the region. Cochran formula for unknown population is used to determine the sample size. The method determines the minimal sample size needed for a study involving categorical data by taking into account the margin of error, projected proportion, and confidence level. The appropriate sample size given the specified combination of precision, confidence, and variability is 139. This study was opened to students of all genders who are currently enrolled in grades 11 and 12.

2.3. Research instruments

The research tool that was utilized in the study is categorized into five parts, namely i) Part I: Demographic profiling; ii) Part II: Media reading preference scale [11]; iii) Part III: Text type preference; iv) Part IV: Reading amount [12]; and v) Part V: Motivations for reading questionnaire (MRQ) [13]. For Part V, the researchers used eight scales from the original 11 scales of the MRQ. The 8 scales that were used specifically measure students' intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation. The scales used include curiosity, involvement, preference for challenge, recognition, grades, social, competition, and compliance. In this study, a revised MRQ was adapted to contextualize the items to electronic text. This questionnaire was presented on a 4-point Likert scale.

2.4. Data analysis

This study made use of descriptive statistics to calculate, describe, and summarize the collected research data in a logical, meaningful, and efficient way. Frequencies mean, and standard deviations were utilized to analyze the different variables of the study. The data was analyzed using a cross-tabulation method, which will allow the researchers to identify patterns, trends, and/or correlations within the study parameters. On the other hand, this method uses a basic tabular form to draw inferences between different data sets in the research study. Pearson correlation was also used to see if there is any significant relationship between students' media preferences and their reading motivation.

2.5. Ethical considerations

This study ensured that people participated voluntarily. Before accepting or declining to participate in the study, participants were informed of its goal, benefits, and pitfalls. In the survey instruments, participants were not compelled to disclose their identities. Anonymity was maintained throughout to safeguard both the participants and the data obtained from them. Personal identifying information was not displayed to prevent it from being linked to other data by others.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Media reading format preferences

The emergence of studies on reading preference (electronic texts vs. print texts) in the last decade reflects society's sudden shift to digital products and inputs [14]–[16]. Despite changes in the materials that students use to complete their classwork, students continue to rely on both print and non-print materials. Table 1 presents the SHS students' media reading format preferences in terms of their perceived usability.

Table 1. Media reading format preferences

Types of media		Preference level					Rank
		5	4	3	2	1	
eBooks (PDF books and Kindle)	f	41	63	49	22	26	4
	%	20.4	31.3	24.4	10.9	12.9	
Mail (Email)	f	40	56	44	37	24	5
	%	19.9	27.9	21.9	18.4	11.9	
Websites (Blogs and Wikipedia)	f	56	66	44	17	18	3
	%	27.9	32.8	21.9	8.5	9	
Social media networks (Facebook posts and Instagram posts)	f	63	50	47	24	17	2
	%	31.3	24.9	23.4	11.9	8.5	
Books (Physical books, school books, and pocket books)	f	85	47	34	13	20	1
	%	43.3	23.4	16.9	6.5	10	
Newspapers (Sunstar, Philippine Daily Inquirer, and Manila Bulletin)	f	32	40	65	38	32	6
	%	15.9	19.9	32.3	18.9	15.9	
Magazines (Metro magazine and Yes magazine)	f	16	37	61	51	36	7
	%	8	18.4	30.3	25.4	17.9	

Based on Table 1, 43.4% of the respondents (85 student respondents) strongly prefer the use of books (physical books, school books, and pocketbooks) in their daily school activities. Despite the prevalence of other forms of media, students still prefer to use physical books to aid learning. On the other hand, students moderately-strongly prefer the use of websites, which corresponds to 32.8% (66 student respondents). This agrees with some studies [14], [17] which state that students still prefer print texts over electronic texts for reasons like portability, familiarity, useful features for note-taking, and an option for dog-eared pages. Several respondents used websites as well wherein asynchronous e-learning web-based modules can be used for learning activities. Using the internet has improved collaboration among students and teachers by allowing

them to share bookmarks that they find interesting. When students use the internet to learn, they can get immediate feedback and ask questions.

The data, on the other hand, shows that 17.9% of students preferred (or least preferred) to use magazines. However, another study contradicted that reading newspapers and magazines (69.5%) is most preferred by a group of faculty members and students, which is followed by books (58.9%) and reference sources (24.4%) [18]. According to the preceding discussions, despite the rise of electronic materials, students continue to use print materials, such as books, for learning. Students continue to rely heavily on websites and other web sources, but they do not completely replace books. Though magazines are widely regarded as the least preferred media format, this does not mean that these publications are no longer beneficial to students.

3.2. Text type preference

The types of texts that students choose to read reflect their reading motivation and level. As a result, it is critical to understand the types of texts they prefer to read, both traditionally and digitally. The National Literacy Trust survey [16], indicates that the types of text read vary depending on the device used. The survey posits that news and non-fiction were read more frequently on computers and smartphones, while fiction was read more frequently on e-readers and tablets. It was also discovered that non-fiction texts were read less frequently in print than on electronic devices such as computers and e-readers. Table 2 shows the respondents' preferred text types for academic and non-academic readings.

Table 2. Text type preference

Text types (Academic and non-academic texts)	f	%	Rank
I prefer reading academic texts in electronic format.	25	12.4	4
I prefer reading academic texts in print format.	97	48.3	1
I prefer reading nonacademic texts in electronic format.	29	14.4	3
I prefer reading nonacademic texts in print format.	17	8.5	5
Undecided	33	16.4	2

Based on Table 2, there is a huge difference in the number of students who utilize print and electronic formats for both academic and non-academic texts and readings. 48.3% (97 student respondents) of the respondents prefer reading academic texts in print formats, while 12.4% (25 student respondents) prefer reading them in electronic format. In a survey conducted with 177 library and information science students in Israel, it was found that students still prefer printed materials [19]. A similar finding also reported that students preferred reading course materials and textbooks in print and felt they learned better this way supported by an eye-tracking test, which revealed that most students only used print-format features such as highlighting and taking notes [20]. The eye-tracking reading tests identified some differences between print and digital reading behaviors, including pupils navigating differently in digital format by skimming and flipping back and forth more than in print, and participants spent more time focusing on the print text. Another study supported the notion that students prefer print over electronic media for learning, but their actual behavior is influenced by a variety of factors, including accessibility, cost, difficulty, and the value of the reading to the course [21]. Despite several studies supporting the fact that students prefer print materials, some identify the use of electronic formats as accessible and convenient. Most students still prefer print format over digital for their academic readings, however, they like the convenience and accessibility of electronic sources and materials [22]. The widespread of these materials online has also augmented the concern about the limited SHS resources available for teacher use [23].

Meanwhile, 14.4% (or 29 student respondents) read non-academic texts in electronic format. It can also be seen that 8.5% (or 17 student respondents) preferred reading non-academic texts in print format. In a previous study, it was discovered that social media text-based exercises were successful in increasing students' familiarity with both academic and non-academic language [24]. In the digital age, students frequently read and write on social media sites for non-academic objectives using colloquial language, thus supporting the idea of their preference to use electronic media (which could include web sources, social media, and e-books) for non-academic or leisure reading. However, some researchers indicated that a majority of students preferred reading adventure novels and stories (non-academic or leisure) on printed resources [25]. The respondents reported that physical page flipping is still superior to swiping on screens or using digital books when reading these types of materials. On the other hand, according to the data presented, students prefer different text formats for academic and non-academic reading materials. Physical resources are still used for academic readings, whereas digital or online resources are prevalently used for non-academic or leisure reading.

3.3. Reading amount

While the data surrounding the mediating role of reading amount to the relationship between reading motivation and reading achievement have been inconsistent [26], [27], the apparent role of reading amount to students' reading motivation and achievement have consistently been noted in many types of research [28]–[30]. The emergence of new media reading formats in recent years has further intensified the need to look into the reading amount of the students both in print texts and electronic texts. This is to keep up with the new ways students consume reading materials. Table 3 details the reading amount of the students both in print and electronic texts.

Table 3. Reading amount

	Print texts (books, newspapers, magazines)		Electronic texts (eBooks, emails, websites, social media networks)	
	f	%	f	%
More than 3 hours a week	49	24.4	58	28.9
Between 1 to 3 hours a week	67	33.3	95	47.3
Less than 1 hour a week	66	32.8	37	18.4
I do not read (print/ electronic texts)	19	9.5	11	5.5

Table 3 shows that senior high school students generally spend less than 1 hour to 3 hours a week reading print texts (books, newspapers, and magazines). Specifically, 33.3% (67 respondents) spend 1 hour to 3 hours a week reading print texts. Another 32.8% (66 respondents) spend less than 1 hour a week reading print texts. Studies showed a general trend of spending less than 1 hour to 3 hours per week reading print texts [12] and affirmed that the average reading amount of students at half an hour to an hour [28].

In terms of students' electronic text reading amount, a whopping 47.3% (95 respondents) spend 1 hour to 3 hours a week reading electronic texts (e-books, emails, websites, and social media networks). A decent 28.9% (58 respondents) read electronic texts for more than 3 hours a week. According to a study, scrolling on a tablet improved reading experiences [31]. This finding may have consequences for how teachers teach reading in classrooms where reading context and activities are provided for students. In contrast to this, a study showed fewer students reading electronic texts in the range of 1 hour to more than 3 hours a week [12]. This finding is interesting because, despite the strong preference of students to print formats as shown in Tables 1 and 2, they still spend more time reading electronic texts than reading print texts. This may have stemmed from the broad nature of electronic texts and the prevalence of social media use both for interacting with people and for written text (information) consumption.

3.4. Reading motivation type

As established in the first parts of this paper, motivation plays a pivotal role in reading achievement. Taking a closer look at the types of motivation learners have in reading can help educators and curriculum developers craft lessons, materials, and activities that are suitable to students' motivation types. Table 4 shows the ranking of eight different motivation scales adapted from the original 11 motivation scales [13]. These scales can be grouped into two general motivation types, intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation.

Long-term reading habits can be influenced by a person's perceived ability to accomplish reading tasks effectively and how highly they value reading. It was also found out that the value attached to reading was significantly tied to their motivation to read [32]. In this study, Table 4 shows that the intrinsic motivation scales (curiosity, involvement, and preference for a challenge) significantly outranked most extrinsic motivation scales (recognition, grades, social, competition, and compliance). Specifically, the involvement scale ranked 1st with a mean of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.68. This is followed by another intrinsic motivation scale, curiosity, at 2nd with a mean of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 0.63. The scale that ranked 3rd is grades, an extrinsic motivation scale, with a mean of 2.91 and a standard deviation of 0.79. Tied in the 4th rank is the preference for a challenge (intrinsic motivation scale) and recognition (extrinsic motivation scale) with means of 2.88 and respective standard deviations of 0.70 and 0.91. The rest of the ranking consisted of extrinsic motivation scales. This means that students are generally more intrinsically motivated to read than extrinsically. This agrees with a study which found that both poor and good readers, although motivated both intrinsically and extrinsically, are generally more intrinsically motivated [33], [34]. It is important to note that while intrinsic motivation is generally more dominant in senior high school students, one motivation type does not exist exclusively. This is especially shown in the data on the rank of the scale of grades, with an extrinsic motivation scale outranking one of the intrinsic motivation scales. This means that in developing curriculum, lessons, and materials, focusing stiffly on one dominant motivation type will not be good for all students.

Table 4. Reading motivation type

Statements	Mean	SD	Rank
If I am reading about an interesting topic, I sometimes lose track of time.	3.11	0.94	
I read stories about fantasy and make-believe.	3.15	0.98	
I like mystery stories.	3.29	0.89	
I make pictures in my mind when I read.	3.48	0.87	
I feel like I made friends with people in good books.	2.93	1.02	
I like to read a lot of adventure stories.	3.16	0.92	
I enjoy a long, involved story or fiction book.	3.14	0.95	
INVOLVEMENT	3.18	0.68	1
I like to read because I always feel happy when I read things that are of interest to me.	3.24	0.91	
If the teacher discusses something interesting, I might read more about it.	3.22	0.87	
I have favorite subjects that I like to read about.	3.21	0.9	
I read to learn new information about topics that interest me.	3.3	0.82	
I read about my hobbies to learn more about them.	3.14	0.86	
I like to read about new things.	3.14	0.92	
I enjoy reading books about people in different countries.	2.72	0.98	
CURIOSITY	3.14	0.63	2
Grades are a good way to see how well you are doing in reading.	2.74	0.97	
I look forward to finding out my grades in tasks that include reading.	2.91	0.97	
I like to read to improve my grades.	3.08	0.89	
GRADES	2.91	0.79	3
I like getting compliments about how well I read from my teacher.	2.87	1	
I like having my friends sometimes tell me I am a good reader.	2.85	1	
I like to get compliments on my reading.	2.85	1.05	
I am happy when someone recognizes my reading.	2.95	0.98	
RECOGNITION	2.88	0.91	4
I like hard, challenging books.	2.61	0.92	
If the project is interesting, I can read difficult material.	2.74	0.88	
I like it when the questions in books make me think.	2.99	0.94	
I usually learn difficult things by reading.	3.07	0.91	
If a book is interesting, I don't care how hard it is to read.	3.01	0.91	
PREFERENCE FOR CHALLENGE	2.88	0.7	4
I always do my reading work exactly as the teacher wants it.	2.73	0.9	
Finishing every assignment that involves reading is important to me.	2.87	0.97	
I always try to finish my reading on time.	2.86	0.94	
COMPLIANCE	2.82	0.79	5
I try to get more answers right than my friends.	2.29	1.05	
I like to finish my reading before other students.	2.3	1.02	
I like being the only one who knows the answer to something we read.	2.22	1.13	
I am willing to work hard to read better than my friends.	2.25	1.03	
COMPETITION	2.27	0.91	6
I like to visit the library often with my family.	1.89	0.93	
I often like to read to my brother or my sister.	1.87	0.96	
My friends and I like to trade things to read.	2.41	1.06	
I like to talk to my friends about what I am reading.	2.92	1.08	
I like to tell my family about what I am reading.	2.08	1.07	
SOCIAL	2.23	0.74	7

3.5. Correlation between students' new and conventional media preferences and reading motivation

Table 5 shows the correlation between the various new and conventional media tools and reading motivation among SHS students. The analysis revealed that students' preference for E-books (PDF books, and Kindle) has a significant positive relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .381, p < .01$), involvement scale ($r = .360, p < .01$), preference for challenge scale ($r = .224, p < .01$), and grades scale ($r = .161, p < .05$). This suggests that the stronger the preference of students for E-books, the higher their motivation is in terms of addressing questions about texts read (curiosity), connection to the material read (involvement), preference for challenge, and need for good grades. Another study affirmed the role of E-book reading in increasing students' intrinsic motivation to read [35]. What is interesting about the data is the significant positive relationship between students' preference for E-books and the extrinsic scale, grades. This means that aside from intrinsic motivation to read, students also read eBooks to improve their grades.

Students' preference for the new media, mail (email), also has a significant positive relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .385, p < .01$), involvement scale ($r = .332, p < .01$), preference for challenge scale ($r = .270, p < .01$), recognition scale ($r = .174, p < .05$), grades scale ($r = .178, p < .05$), and compliance scale ($r = .204, p < .01$). This indicates that the stronger the preference of students for mail, the higher their motivation is in terms of knowing the content of a text (curiosity), connection to the material read (involvement), preference for challenge, being recognized in their capacity to read (recognition), need for good grades, and the need to check on reading tasks via mail (compliance). This data generally shows the strong intrinsic and extrinsic motivation traction of emails to students. This means that emails can be leveraged by educators to improve the reading

skills of students by not only using them as a means of communication but also as channels for the delivery and consumption of reading materials.

Table 5. Correlations between new media preference and reading motivation (n=201)

Types of media		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
eBooks	Pearson Correlation	.381**	.360**	.224**	0.120	.161*	-0.063	-0.021	0.085
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.091	0.022	0.376	0.768	0.232
Mail (Email)	Pearson Correlation	.385**	.332**	.270**	.174*	.178*	0.104	0.067	.204**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.013	0.011	0.143	0.342	0.004
Websites	Pearson Correlation	.352**	.397**	.178*	0.104	0.120	-0.017	-0.035	0.048
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.012	0.140	0.091	0.810	0.625	0.496
Social media	Pearson Correlation	.257**	.245**	0.117	0.101	0.114	0.045	0.010	0.123
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.098	0.153	0.108	0.525	0.887	0.081
Books	Pearson Correlation	.424**	.424**	.367**	0.108	.190**	0.033	0.039	.208**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.127	0.007	0.640	0.587	0.003
Newspapers	Pearson Correlation	.296**	.292**	.310**	0.138	.198**	.160*	0.080	.203**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.050	0.005	0.023	0.259	0.004
Magazines	Pearson Correlation	.300**	.226**	.274**	0.107	.188**	.186**	.189**	.243**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.131	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.001

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Students' preference for websites (blogs and Wikipedia) has a significant positive relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .352$, $p < .01$), involvement scale ($r = .397$, $p < .01$), and preference for challenge scale ($r = .178$, $p < .05$). This suggests that the stronger their preference for websites, the more motivated they are in terms of their interest in reading online texts (curiosity), connection to the material read (involvement), and preference for a challenge. This means that, as a whole, intrinsic motivation to read has a significant positive relationship with students' preference for websites. This finding supports that of a study which showed students' positive perception of the use of the Internet as a learning medium in reading classrooms [36]. This data is also very telling of the important role of texts found on the internet in making sure that students continue to read outside the classroom setting since students' motivation for reading texts found on websites stems internally.

Students' preference for social media networks (Facebook posts and Instagram posts) has a significant positive relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .257$, $p < .01$) and involvement scale ($r = .245$, $p < .01$). This means that the stronger their preference for social media, the more motivated they are in terms of their interest in reading online posts and their connection to the post read. This also means that like students' preference for websites, students' preference for social media networks is mainly due to their intrinsic motivation to read. This is in congruence with the result of another study which showed intrinsic motivation as an important factor that influences reading motivation among social media users [37].

Students' preference for books (physical books, school books, and pocket books) has a significant positive relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .424$, $p < .01$), involvement scale ($r = .424$, $p < .01$), preference for a challenge ($r = .367$, $p < .01$), recognition ($r = .190$, $p < .01$), and compliance ($r = .208$, $p < .01$). This implies that the stronger their preferences for books, the higher their motivation is in terms of addressing questions about texts read (curiosity), connection to the material read (involvement), preference for challenge, being recognized in their capacity to read (recognition) and complying with reading tasks given by teachers (compliance). Research results confirmed students' strong preference for printed books for their academic needs [38]. Interestingly, a study strongly supports the relationship between reading books and compliance since study results indicate the highest percentage of students use their textbooks only when their instructors require them to do so [12]. This implies that students continue to rely heavily on printed materials and are likely to do so in the future because doing so satisfies their curiosity, improves their reading experience, and allows them to meet academic requirements.

Students' preference for print media (newspapers, namely: Sunstar, Philippine Daily Inquirer, and Manila Bulletin) has a significant relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .296$, $p < .01$), involvement ($r = .292$, $p < .01$), preference for a challenge ($r = .310$, $p < .01$), grades ($r = .198$, $p < .01$), social ($r = .160$, $p < .05$), and compliance ($r = .203$, $p < .01$). This suggests that the stronger their preferences for newspapers, the higher their motivation is in terms of addressing and learning about current events (curiosity), connection to the materials read (involvement), gaining new knowledge through reading technical texts found in newspapers (preference for a challenge), getting better grades by completing reading tasks (grades), socializing and connecting with others (social), and complying with academic requirements (compliance). A study on headline curiosity and news consumption [39] suggests a relationship between newspaper consumption and curiosity. Results indicate

that people are most likely to consume newspapers when it arouses their curiosity, for instance, news articles appear to pose salient and more important questions. It can also be inferred that it is closely related to involvement and social factors since people tend to talk about current events and have a greater tendency to do in-depth reading and research (preference for a challenge). Newspaper reading is also found to be an effective tool for vocabulary and reading skills building, making language teachers require several newspaper readings during the academic year. A gradual increase in students' vocabulary and reading as a result of newspaper reading activities incorporated into language course requirements is promising [40].

Students' preference for magazines (Metro magazine and !Yes magazine) has a significant relationship with the curiosity scale ($r = .300, p < .01$), involvement ($r = .226, p < .01$), preference for a challenge ($r = .274, p < .01$), grades ($r = .188, p < .01$), social ($r = .186, p < .01$), competition ($r = .189, p < .01$), and compliance ($r = .243, p < .01$). This implies that the stronger their preferences for magazines (as a form of print media), the higher their motivation is in terms of addressing questions about texts read (curiosity), connection to the material read (involvement), preference for challenge, need for good grades (grades), socializing and connecting with others (social), being considered knowledgeable about issues and concepts (competition), and complying with reading tasks given by teachers (compliance). Similarly, a study reported that all the respondents of the study used newspapers and magazines as sources of information [41]. The majority of them opted to read the entertainment and sports sections. A greater number showed more interest in reading entertainment and fashion magazines, thus addressing their curiosity, and involvement, being perceived as knowledgeable for their capacity to recall and discuss the latest news and events (competition) and to connect and socialize with others through discussions about the materials read. The same study also reveals how the respondents saw magazines as resources that can inspire them to read, broaden their horizons (curiosity), enhance their general knowledge, and improve their reading comprehension (preference for a challenge). It is also believed that by utilizing magazines (and other print media like newspapers), students could develop a strong reading habit that will later aid their performance in any academic task.

From the discussions, new and conventional media have an obvious link to senior high school students' reading motivation. However, this relationship is so complex that its implication may not be as straightforward as it may suggest. The data on the components of the new media reading profile of the students, for example, exhibit discrepancies concerning reading preferences (general tip toward physical books) and reading amount (longer time spent on electronic reading). This may have strong implications for designing a curriculum involving the skill of reading, specifically on the channels through which reading materials are delivered. Since the results show that students spend more time reading electronic texts, it would be a good measure to integrate technology with activities involving the skill of reading. Moreover, students' motivation type leans more towards intrinsic motivation. This means that banking on students' interests in the implementation of a reading curriculum is more likely to deliver positive educational results. This is not to say that extrinsic motivation should be overlooked. The data also suggest that students, to some extent, are extrinsically motivated and, therefore must also be taken into consideration in the development of the reading curriculum. Finally, positive relationships between new media reading preference and motivation scales attest to the role of motivation, especially intrinsic, in students' reading.

4. CONCLUSION

The use of media has greatly affected student reading proficiency, as well as reading motivation. The prerequisites of modern education have given reading teachers opportunities and challenges to continue to promote reading among students. Despite the growing popularity of modern media, students still find conventional media significant and relevant in their reading. This suggests that reading teachers may think about using both conventional and new media to support students' reading. Since Gen Z students are accustomed to using new media, teachers can benefit from this and make use of their preferred methods to motivate students to read more. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation is still considered to be one of the substantial reasons why students read. Reading teachers should make sure that students will find what they read to be relevant, more so something they can use in life. This study further concluded that the analysis of student preferences is crucial for reading teachers. Using these data would enable them to devise better strategies for motivating students to read more and significantly improve the senior high school students' reading skills.

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